

Proceeding Paper

Process Engineering for Low-Temperature Carbon-Based Perovskite Solar Modules

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Abstract

In less than a decade, Perovskite solar cell (PSC) technology has gained high efficiency and broad attention because of its key enabling physical and morphological features. One of the main obstacles to PSC industrialization and commercialization is managed with the demonstration of stable devices by adopting low-cost, reliable materials and fabrication process methods. Here, we report a Perovskite solar module based on a low-temperature carbon electrode. The full process was performed in ambient air and engineered by printing techniques.

Keywords

perovskite solar cell; carbon; nanomaterial; low cost; hole transporting layer; stability; printing technique; upscaling; module; processes.

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11 **Abstract:** In less than a decade, Perovskite solar cell (PSC) technology gained high efficiency and the broad attention
12 because of key enabling physical and morphological features. One of the main obstacles to the PSC industrialization
13 and commercialization deals with the demonstration of stable devices by adopting low-cost and reliable materials
14 and fabrication process methods. Here, we report a Perovskite solar module based on a low-temperature carbon
15 electrode. The full process is in ambient air and engineered by printing techniques.

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17 upscaling; module; processes

18

19 **1. Introduction**

20 The photovoltaic (PV) sector has the fundamental role to cover the energy demand caused by the constant
21 and never-ending technology progress [1]. To date, the PV market is based mainly on the “first genera-
22 tion” technology, i.e. monocrystalline and polycrystalline silicon. Despite that, the expensive manufactur-
23 ing processes of silicon and its decreasing availability in nature have accelerated the “second generation”
24 thin-film technologies exploitation based on materials such as cadmium telluride (CdTe) and amorphous
25 silicon (a-Si) [2]. The “third generation” PV based on hybrid-organic materials was born to keep high
26 efficiency by reducing process fabrication costs [3–6]. Natural dyes such as anthocyanins [7], polymers
27 [8] or fullerenes [9] are just a few examples of molecules used for this purpose. The main issues concerning
28 these new technologies are the stability and the upscaling from lab scale cells (area <1 cm²) to modules
29 (interconnection of cells) [10].

30 In the recent years, Perovskite (PVSK) gained attention from scientists and investors because of its op-
31 tical and electronic properties allowing a continuous development reaching record efficiencies (close to
32 26%)[11–14]. PVSK is a chemical compound with ABX₃ formula, where A and B are cations with different
33 atomic radii and X represents an anion. PVSK-based materials organometallic compounds of halogens
34 have gathered particular interest in PV field thanks to the easy processability by solution-based methods
35 [15].

36 Each layer forming a PVSK solar cell (PSC) has a well-defined function affecting the performance and the
37 stability of the device. The PVSK is sandwiched between one electron transport layer (ETL) and a hole
38 transport layer (HTL). ETL and HTL are both connected to an external circuit by gold or silver contacts.
39 In case of the n-i-p architecture, ETL is generally composed by c-TiO₂ (compact TiO₂) and mp-TiO₂ (mes-
40 oporous TiO₂) or SnO₂ and guarantee good conduction, low charge recombination and high transparency.
41 The most widespread HTM (hole transporting material) is the 2,2',7,7'-Tetrakis(N,Ndi-p-methoxyphenyl-
42 amine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene. Spiro-MeOTAD ensures good energy levels of band gap, quick charge trans-
43 fer and low recombination, however it has low stability, high cost (about 200 euro/g), complex synthesis
44 and low yield [16]. Moreover, spiro-OMeTAD is doped to increase the mobility of the holes with highly
45 hygroscopic salts (lithiumbis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (Li-TFSI) or 4-tert-butylpyridine (t-BP)) lead-
46 ing to PSC degradation deterioration. About the metal counter-electrode, gold diffuses into the structure
47 of the device when exposed to continuous lighting, causing huge PVSK degradation. Both the organic

1 HTL and the metal electrode can be replaced with one low temperature conductive carbon layer. Carbon
 2 materials are cheap if compared to HTMs and gold, resulting in a reduction of cells cost and an increase
 3 in stability. Carbon is a key material widely used in the PV field due to its abundance, low cost, and
 4 appropriate energy level. In the PVSK field, low temperature carbon pastes, unlike the porous high tem-
 5 perature inks [17,18], can be processed at temperatures below 130 °C exhibiting features of high conduc-
 6 tivity, low cost, good stability and high throughput process [18–23].

7 In this paper, we demonstrate a simple process based on scalable printing techniques out of glove-box to
 8 fabricate a gold-free perovskite solar module (PSM) based on low temperature carbon counter-electrode.

9 2. Materials and Methods

10 The 31.36 cm² module (active area 6.25 cm²) is fabricated by interconnecting in series four n-i-p cells. The
 11 stack of each cell and the device process fabrication steps are depicted in Figure 1a and Figure 1b, respec-
 12 tively.

13

(c)

18 **Figure 1.** (a) PSC layers; (b) Module fabrication process steps; (c) Module IV curves in reverse and forward scan.

18 A nanosecond raster Nd:YVO₄ pulsed scanning laser patterned (P1, fluence=10.5 J/cm²) the FTO (fluori-
 19 nated tin oxide) glasses (NSG, 7 Ω/sq) to form 4 series connected cells. Then, we cleaned the substrates in
 20 an ultrasonic system by using subsequent solvents (soap/water, acetone, ethanol and isopropanol) for 5
 21 min each. We deposited 40 nm thick c-TiO₂ as reported in [24] and 250 nm thick mp-TiO₂ paste (Great
 22 Cell Solar 18 nrt, diluted with ethanol 1:4 *w/w*) by blade coating method followed by 30 min@500 °C
 23 sintering in oven. The substrates are exposed to an UV lamp and then we deposited the triple cation PVSK
 24 (Cs_{0.05}(MA_{0.17}FA_{0.83})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃) in DMF/DMSO (PbI₂ from TCI Co. Ltd.; CsI, FAI and MABr from
 25 Great Cell Solar) by a double step blade-coating method in ambient air according to Vesce et al. [24]. We
 26 reduced the recombination by depositing PEAI (phenethyl ammonium iodide) passivating agent [25,26].
 27 A stable HTM suitable for carbon was deposited by blade-coating technique. Then, the
 28 ETL/PVSK/PEAI/HTL stack is removed from the vertical connection areas by laser (P2, fluence=200 J/cm²)
 29 to series connect two adjacent cells by the counter-electrode. Following this, the carbon counter-electrode
 30 (Dyemaco) is blade-coated on the cells composing the module and annealed at 120 °C in air for 15 min.

1 The IV curves are reported by a Keithley source meter/LabVIEW under a class A sun simulator (Sun 2000,
2 Abet) at AM 1.5 1000 W/m² calibrated by a Skye Instruments sensor Ltd.

4 3. Results and Discussion

5 In the upscaling process from lab-scale cell to module there are different issues to be considered: the high
6 front contact sheet resistance, the interconnection dead area and resistance, the layer inhomogeneity. In
7 this work, we apply reliable mitigation action to reduce the losses. The sheet resistance is faced by using
8 low sheet resistance substrate, by adopting the series interconnection strategy and by optimizing the cell
9 width (i.e. reducing the recombination path). The interconnection dead area is reduced by narrowing the
10 interconnection and separation areas. The laser process optimization is useful to limit the interconnection
11 resistance. The layer homogeneity is achieved by combining the right coating technique and the material
12 composition according to the deposition environment. Moreover, we worked in ambient air to simulate
13 a real plant condition.

14 In Figure 1c, the fabricated PVSK carbon-based module exhibit 8.36% and 8.25% efficiency in reverse and
15 forward scan, respectively. The Voc is about 4 V meaning about 1 V per cell, because the cells are series
16 connected in Z configuration.

17 4. Conclusion

18 The PV exploitation should avoid high-cost and high-CO₂ footprint materials and fabrication processes.
19 The adoption of low-temperature carbon-based counter-electrodes permits to avoid expensive and un-
20 stable organic HTM and metal counter-electrodes, such as gold or silver. Besides this, the full fabrication
21 process must be based on scalable printing techniques out of glove box to be transferred to industry. In
22 this direction, the carbon inks can be deposited by large area printing techniques, such as screen-printing
23 and blade-coating. Since the carbon layer can be annealed at temperature less than 120 °C, the impact
24 from the LCA (life cycle assessment) point of view is low. Here, we demonstrated a printed PSM based
25 on low temperature carbon counter-electrode.

26
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29 writing—original draft preparation, L.V.; writing—review and editing, L.V.; visualization, L.V.; supervision, A.D.C.
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38 **Conflicts of Interest:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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